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All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture

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Circularity Assessment

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Evidence of accomplishment

Report

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1 Summary

This deliverable entails the description of the circularity assessment of integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) production developed in the context of the ASTRAL project. Circularity assessment aimed at evaluating the performance of 4 IMTA labs compared to monoculture conditions. To do so, a framework was defined to address all the aspects concerning the application of circularity in IMTA production.

Firstly, an interactive process with the IMTA-Labs partners was conducted to identify actions that directly contributed to the circular economy. Based on the main pillars defined (use of resources and nutrient management), indicators were defined to evaluate the 4 IMTA labs. Data sourced from the project research activities and literature data were collected to quantify the corresponding indicators. Finally, the evolution of these parameters through the experimental periods and comparing them to baseline conditions (monoculture) offered valuable information on how well the systems were performing in terms of circular economy. Results showed an increase of circularity up to 90% in terms of water recirculation, as well as bioremediation improved by 80-90%, providing evidence on the potential role of IMTA in the circularity transition.

The approach defined provides the industry with a framework that allows the assessment of circularity in aquaculture without increasing the burden on producers and operators in terms of data collection, but which provides metrics based on indicators with a scientific evidence base.

2 Introduction

2.1 Circular aquaculture

To mitigate environmental impacts and increase production efficiency circular economy is pointed out as driver for a sustainable development, as recognised within the policies launched at the European level¹⁻³. As part of the strategy for a sustainable development of aquaculture, the Commission recommends environmental performance improvement through the adoption of the circular approach and waste management⁴.

Although circular economy definition acquires multiple forms and meanings depending on the point of view⁵, the definition based on examples of circularity implementation practices would be a good approach to harmonize the concept. Essentially, circular economy is a model of production and consumption where cleaner and more competitive practices are focusing on saving and recovering resources¹.

As well as the definition, the typology of examples is also very wide in the specific case of aquaculture and no publication can be found that provides a state of the art of the real and actual implementation of the circular economy in this sector⁶. The circular aquaculture concept has very different angles from which it can be addressed⁷, but generally circularity in aquaculture includes the adoption of practices regarding waste management^{8 9 10}, recycling of nutrients^{11 12 13 14}, or the incorporation of novel ingredients in feeds derived from the bio-economy^{15 16}.

Some ecological principles potentially guide biomass use towards circular economy¹⁷ and how these principles can be applicable to aquaculture is part of the recent study of Chary *et al.* (2023)⁶. The priorities identified in that work increase the circularity in aquaculture mainly through the decrease of waste, the nutrient recycling and the adaptation of aquafeed formulations. Therefore, it seems that a more circular aquaculture must be in line with the conventional R-framework principles: reduce, recycle, recover.

Looking into the different aquaculture production models, circular approaches can be observed as inherent attributes of farm operations. On the one hand, recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) are pointed out as an opportunity to increase circularity in aquaculture in the sense that RAS increase the efficiency of water use by filtering the wastewater while making the improvement of waste collection possible¹⁸. Wastewater from RAS systems contain high concentrations of solids and nutrients, which can be useful resources if treated effectively⁷. Furthermore, RAS allows the production of aquaculture species under a controlled rearing environment and can also reduce the carbon footprint when combined with the use of renewable energy¹⁸. Not only in terms of waste stream management, but also in terms of resource use, RAS facilitates lower feed conversion rates comparing to net-pen production systems¹⁹.

On the other hand, in pond aquaculture, nutrients runoff from surrounding fields might potentially contribute sufficient fertilization of ponds^{20 21}, which can be understood as a circular practice in terms of nutrient recycling of surrounding bio-economy activities and efficient use of resources in aquaculture. Beyond circularity, the contribution of ponds to ecosystem services is also recognized²², particularly as supporting services regarding the role of ponds in natural nutrient cycles²³.

Open culture systems, such as fish aquaculture in cages, make use of water from natural environment and commonly face challenges related to (real or perceived) impacts upon the surrounding aquatic environment²⁴. Although some studies point to the environmental benefits due to the dilution of emissions from cages in open systems²⁵, the collection, recovery and recycling of these nutrients are of main concern to promote the implementation of circular practices. In this regard, integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) is the production of species from different trophic levels, where uneaten feed and nutrient losses can be recaptured and converted into valuable nutrients for additional harvestable seafood and crops²⁶. In IMTA schemes, different species, such as fish, invertebrates, and seaweeds, are strategically integrated to create a symbiotic relationship where each organism contributes to the overall health of the ecosystem in the same region^{27 28}. Bioremediation capabilities play a crucial role in IMTA systems by utilizing the natural metabolic activities of various organisms to remediate and improve water quality^{29 30 31}. This approach promotes a circular economy within aquaculture, where waste from one component becomes a valuable resource for others³².

Fish excrete inorganic nitrogenous and phosphorylated emissions, which can be utilized by cultivated seaweeds as a nutrient source for growth, thus reducing nutrient levels in the water and preventing eutrophication⁹. Additionally, filter-feeding organisms, like bivalves such as mussels or oysters, can help in the removal of small particulate organic matter and nutrients by efficiently filtering water³³. Larger particulate organic matter can be recovered by other invertebrates, such as sea urchins and sea cucumbers. Bioremediation is therefore interpreted as a circular attribute of IMTA as it promotes the recycling of nutrients.

2.2 Circularity metrics

In the manner it operates at different levels, circularity should be measurable through indicators also at different scales. Some authors^{34 35} identify the macro-scale as the level relates to cities, regions, countries and beyond; the meso-scale relates to industrial synergies and micro-scale level relates to products, services or companies.

At European level, currently there is no single set of indicators for the assessment of the environmental sustainability of aquaculture³⁶ and the indicators developed by JRC for the monitoring of the EU Bioeconomy³⁷ do not include indicators for the evaluation of the circularity performance. A potential new indicator on nutrient discharge from marine aquaculture has been suggested by the European

Commission and it is under evaluation³⁸. Nutrient discharge data could be directly linked to the study of the circularity performance since it would potentially provide information on the efficiency of nutrient cycling. National scales can provide an economy-wide perspective and help to evaluate whether absolute reduction in resource use and waste flows³⁹.

Following the premise “What gets measured gets managed”, the product-level approach may be the most useful for business stakeholders⁴⁰. A good approach for the evaluation of aquaculture products has been provided by Valentí *et al.* (2018)⁴¹, where quantitative indicators are defined addressing the three dimensions of sustainability through 56 indicators for the economic, environmental and social attributes. This framework provides indicator for the evaluation of efficiency through the quantification of natural resources use, which would perfectly link to the evaluation of some circularity attributes. Complementary, aspects such as natural resource depletion, in-use stock growth, and the useful service lifetime should consider as essential indicators³⁴ at product or material level; however, no harmonization exists regarding the most appropriate framework for the measurement of circularity indicators^{42 43}. In addition to the fact that most CE metrics focus on the technical cycle and materials from non-renewable resources⁴³, none of the approaches reviewed at micro-level fulfil the particularities of aquaculture production, discouraging the communication of circular attributes from the farms. Complementary, the diversity of aquaculture systems makes it challenging to determine the circular profile of the sector under the same approach.

Linder *et al.*⁴⁰, provide a comparison between different product-level circularity metrics, concluding that none of the existing metrics highly score across all criteria (validity, reliability, transparency, and generality)⁴⁰. As addressed in the paper mentioned before, the Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) is pointed out as an appropriate approach for the circularity of products, as published by Macarthur (2015). Although the revised version included the biological cycles within the approach, originally the MCI was developed to measure the circularity of technical products⁴⁴. It is, therefore, apparently difficult to associate concepts such as utility (referring to durability or usage intensity) and lifespan to biological products. Moreover, MCI refers to use-phase which has a different interpretation depending on the focus and objective of the circularity analysis. For example, when aquaculture feed is ingested and assimilated by fish (both processes are part of use-phase), feed is transformed into nutrients released to the environment in the form of excretions and faeces, to which the uneaten fraction is added. Therefore, the concept of waste from the use-phase within the MCI approach is not applicable as the flows are transformed (ingredients into nutrients). Though, if the focus is at the nutrient level, circularity can be addressed through the evaluation of nutrients entering and leaving during the aquaculture production period.

A first approximation to adapt circularity metrics to aquaculture was developed in the context of the EU project iFishIENci (GA 818036)⁴⁵, where MCI was re-defined to evaluate the performance of nutrients circularity in new value chains. In carrying this out, the digestibility of feed was selected as a key parameter to evaluate the utility factor, based on experimental data sourced from the assimilation of nutrient studies. Furthermore, the adaptation of the MCI considered that virgin components in feed were the ingredients sourced from non-valorisation routes (conventional sources). In this sense, nitrogen (in the form of proteins) sourced from microalgae cultivated with substrate from aquaculture were interpreted as non-virgin flows, leading to decreasing the linearity, therefore, increasing the MCI indicator.

Given that circularity should be a driver for sustainability, it is also relevant to highlight the role of the sustainability assessment in aquaculture to evaluate environmental aspects⁴⁶. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a very appropriate and ISO- standardized methodology (ISO 14040, 14044), where the impact assessment provides relevant indicators linked to circularity: in terms of nutrient management (through the study of eutrophication impact category) or resource use (with material resource depletion impact category). In this context, and aiming at developing harmonised set of rules to calculate the environmental footprint profile in aquaculture, the Marine Product Environmental Footprint initiative, started in 2014, is contextualised within the EU policy for sustainable production and consumption, specifically within the “single market for green products” policy⁴⁷. Despite providing guidance for the evaluation and subsequent environmental improvement of aquaculture products, it is only applicable to marine fish, not including freshwater fish or low-trophic aquaculture species in the scope.

In the context of the ASTRAL project, sustainability is addressed through the three usual dimensions: environmental, economic, and societal aspects. On the one hand, the environmental profile of IMTA systems is part of D4.3. On the other hand, the implications of IMTA in terms of socio-economic aspects are addressed in a separated work in WP6.

The present deliverable is contextualized within Task 4.2. It is not the aim of this study to provide indicators from the life cycle assessment (LCA) that were covered in Task 4.3, but to perform the circularity assessment of IMTA through the definition and quantification of specific indicators for monitoring the progress on the implementation of circular strategies.

3 Methodology

The circularity performance of aquaculture systems can be evidenced through the study of resource use efficiency and nutrient management, which can be determined in accordance with the capacity to collect and use nutrients and uneaten feed fraction.

In the context of the ASTRAL project, Task 4.2 aimed to provide an evaluation of the circularity performance of the IMTA production through the study of 4 different IMTA labs that were compared to monoculture conditions.

Figure 1 shows the main actions carried out by the ASTRAL IMTA labs that are highlighted through the different colour boxes. These lab-actions were associated with the principle identified in the study developed by Chary *et al.* (2023). As can be derived from this analysis, we identified that IMTA production directly links to the 4th principle (“*using and recycling byproducts of agro and aquatic ecosystems*”) as IMTA can recycle nutrients internally decreasing the emissions to the environment. Moreover, IMTA also promotes circularity by safeguarding and *regenerating* the health of aquatic ecosystems (principle 1) due to the minimization of external inputs and impacts on the environment. It is worth noting that Chary *et al.* refer to by-product and regenerative aquaculture concepts, whereas the ASTRAL project refers to coproduct and restorative aquaculture. With regard to the former, the ASTRAL project addresses the release of nutrients as fluxes that facilitate the cultivation of extractive species. Regarding the latter, we aim to align the terminology to Chopin *et al.*, 2024 when they state that 'regenerative' aquaculture contradicts the original meaning associated with agriculture, where nutrient retention is key⁴⁸.

Figure 1: Identification of circularity principles applied to ASTRAL IMTA labs (based on the study developed by Chary et al., 2023¹)

Similar to other approaches⁴⁹, we focused on measuring IMTA process performance in the context of circularity. To do so, we did not only evaluate the inherent circularity within IMTA systems, but also, we assessed key strategies beyond nutrient recycling that contributed to the circularity of aquaculture, such as the better use of resources at energy, water, infrastructure, and feed level.

From the early stages of the project, the objective was to identify the different actions planned in the IMTA labs that potentially increased the circularity of the systems. This was part of the circularity

¹ This study refers to regenerative aquaculture as the farming approach that uses aquatic ecosystems conservation as the entry point to regenerate and contribute to provisioning, regulating, and supporting ecosystem services.

strategies mapping phase where several meetings were scheduled with the labs partners to understand not only the systems but also the attributes embedded and that were aligned with the circular economy principles. Due to the variety of the production systems, a decision tree was elaborated to guide on the implementation of the circularity assessment (Figure 2). Unlike the IMTA Labs in Ireland, Brazil and South Africa, Scotland IMTA lab did not deploy fed-species, thus circularity of this lab was studied through the infrastructure and equipment needed for the integration of new species.

Figure 2. Circularity assessment framework

3.1 Indicators

Aiming at providing a quantitative analysis of circularity, we developed a set of indicators defined according to the circularity requirements suggested by Vural Gursel *et al.* (2023), to provide metrics aligned with most of the indicators developed in the literature, reflecting⁴³:

- The **resource use efficiency**
- The degree of **recirculation**
- The **utility**
- **The effects on the environment**

The indicators developed for the monitoring of circularity in IMTA systems were defined following the criteria reported by Bannigan *et al.* (2009)⁵⁰, and ensuring the relevance for circularity metrics in line with Corona *et al.* (2019)³⁵.

Together with the characteristics that the indicators should have, the present work focused on the identification of measurable principles of circular economy applied to IMTA systems. In this context, nutrients, and resource use, are fundamental pillars embedded in the applicable principles (as part of safeguarding and *regenerate*, avoid, prioritize, reuse and recycle, and entropy principles). Consequently, the metrics were defined for the evaluation of nutrient recycling and resource use efficiency (figure below), with the aim of providing a comparison of circularity performance between monoculture and IMTA scenario for each lab.

Figure 3. Circularity indicators under circular economy pillars

3.1.1 Nutrient management

We recognized IMTA systems as an aquaculture production system strongly linked to circular economy principles mainly due to nutrient recirculation. Therefore, as part of the essential role of IMTA, bioremediation potential was studied to assess the extent to which extractive species could mitigate nutrients emissions from fed-species.

Nutrient management performance was quantified as part of the evaluation of one of the primary functions of IMTA systems, bioremediation. Within the circularity assessment context, bioremediation is defined as a circularity indicator that informs on the nutrient retention efficiencies, treating waste nutrients from fed species as coproducts that can be recycled by extractive species. Fundamentally, in this integrated system, seaweeds sequester dissolved inorganic nutrients (DIN), shellfish absorb small particulate organic matter (POM), while deposit feeders such as, holothuroids, echinoderms, and polychaetes uptake larger POM.

Various approaches exist to quantify bioremediation, encompassing the measurement of nutrient removal rates, retention capacities, nutrient balances, utilization of tracers (e.g., stable isotopes or fatty acid composition), and modelling techniques¹². Equation 1 shows the approach used to calculate

the bioremediation indicators for carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus through the different trials in both scenarios, monoculture and IMTA.

$$\text{Bioremediation} = \frac{\text{C,N,P emitted by fed-species}}{\text{C,N,P taken up by extractive species}} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

3.1.2 Resource use efficiency

The use of resources was quantified through metrics that reflect the efficiency of IMTA with respect to the intensity in the use of the most relevant resource consumption in aquaculture⁵¹, shown in the next figure:

Figure 4. Main input flows in aquaculture production considered in ASTRAL circularity.

In the ASTRAL project, efficiency in the use of resources was studied in monoculture and IMTA conditions by the quantification and comparison of specific indicators related to feed, water, energy, and materials.

3.1.2.1 Feed

Regarding feed, Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) and circularity of the formulations were defined as the most appropriate indicators (*Equation 2* and *Equation 3*). The FCR is interpreted as equivalent to the use of resources, in the sense that the higher the FCR, the more feed required to produce one unit of fed-species and the less circular (efficient) is the farming. Circularity of formulations was measured based on the linearity concept adapted to aquaculture feeds and developed in the context of the EU project iFishIENCi (GA 818036) detailed in the public report 4.5⁵². The focus of iFishIENCi project was the cultivation of microalgae with substrate derived from aquaculture, and microalgae used for the formulation of new feeds were evaluated as circular ingredient components. In the context of the ASTRAL project, this indicator also reflects the percentage of ingredients that are sourced from valorisation routes in the specific case study of IMTA lab Brazil, where feeding components derived from poultry industry were used in the Fish meal analogue tested. Whenever low trophic species harvested from IMTA schemes were processed and incorporated as feed ingredient in the trials under study, they

were interpreted in the assessment as circular ingredients sourced from valorisation routes. This was the case of IMTA lab (sea urchin) in South Africa, where dried *Ulva* served as feed for sea urchins.

$$\text{FCR} = \left| \frac{\text{Total feed}^2}{\text{fish weight gain}} \right| \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

$$\text{Circularity in formulation} = \frac{\text{Total mass ingredients (g) from valorization routes}}{\text{Total mass of feed delivered}} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

3.1.2.2 Water and Energy

Recirculation efficiency (*Equation 4*) was quantified to reflect the dependency on external water sources, thus being an indicator applicable to semi-closed and closed systems. Complementary, energy indicator (*Equation 5*) was measured through the estimation of energy used by each IMTA lab, in relation to the biomass harvested. Maintenance during the production phase (cleaning pump and foam fractionator) was aggregated as part of the energy indicator and interpreted in terms of kWh. Both water, and energy indicators were defined to reflect the intensity of resource use but not the potential environmental impacts associated with, which was the objective of the previous LCA study (Deliverable 4.3).

$$\text{Water indicator} = \frac{\text{Water recirculated (m}^3\text{)}}{\text{Water in the system (m}^3\text{)}} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

$$\text{Energy indicator} = \frac{\text{kWh consumed}}{\text{biomass harvested}} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

3.1.2.3 Materials

Finally, manufacturing of infrastructure components involves the extraction of resource materials especially steel and fossil-based plastics. An infrastructure indicator (*Equation 2*) was defined to obtain evidence of whether integrated systems promote synergies in the shared use of common elements (for example floating elements) that potentially reduce the use of materials regarding the biomass harvested. In fed-species systems with low trophic species integration, the new materials required are not as many as would be needed in a monoculture scenario due to the synergy effect of the elements. Therefore, the increase of total biomass was interpreted as a major functionality. Functionality was defined as the practicality of the elements for the purpose of enabling biomass growth. Infrastructure indicator was calculated as the total kg of materials within each infrastructure element and correlated to the total biomass developed over the lifespan. Therefore, this indicator was represented as kg infrastructure materials/kg of biomass harvested.

² Feed delivered or ingested depending on the information availability

$$\text{Infrastructure/materials indicator} = \frac{\text{kg infrastructure materials}}{\text{biomass harvested}} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

- **Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)**

In addition to the infrastructure indicator, we identified the relevance of measuring circularity of materials in low trophic aquaculture, due to the recognised role of materials in the overall environmental footprint. In line with another EU project (BIOGEARS, GA 101022432), ASTRAL aimed to assess the impact on circularity of adopting different strategies for the design of IMTA farming structures.

In particular, the Material Circular Indicator (MCI) was identified as an innovative and appropriate approach to evaluate the circularity within materials required for infrastructure, evaluating aspects like the virgin feedstock, waste generation, linearity, and utility. To do so, the adaptation to the aquaculture sector of the methodology developed by the Ellen MacArthur foundation⁵³ was needed. MCI was quantified for IMTA lab in Scotland, where specific actions on infrastructure design were identified. Then MCI was calculated for both, monoculture and IMTA conditions.

The MCI assesses circularity in materials usage, under the following six principles:

1. Sourcing biological materials from sustained sources.
2. Using feedstock from reused or recycled sources.
3. Keeping products in use longer (e.g., by reuse/redistribution/increase durability).
4. Reusing components or recycling materials after the use of the product.
5. Making more intensive use of products (e.g. via service, sharing or performance models).
6. Ensuring biological materials remain uncontaminated and biologically accessible.

Applying this to aquaculture infrastructure involved prioritizing materials with high input circularity, such as recycled plastics or sustainable composites. Considering end-of-life circularity is crucial, emphasizing recyclable materials for infrastructure, aligning with sustainable practices in aquaculture and promoting a circular economy within the industry.

The following parameters were defined by the reference methodology to measure the circularity embedded in materials, and they were adapted to ASTRAL project accordingly.

Virgin Feedstock

Virgin Feedstock indicator (V) represents the fraction of feedstock from virgin sources based on the total mass of the product. It is calculated from the following formula:

$$V = M(1 - F_R - F_U - F_S) \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

Where,

V = Virgin feedstock.

M = Mass of a product.

F_R = Fraction of mass of a product's feedstock from recycled sources.

F_U = Fraction of mass of a product's feedstock from reused sources.

F_S = Fraction of a product's biological feedstock from Sustained Production.

Unrecoverable Waste

Unrecoverable waste poses a challenge to the circularity of a product within a circular economy framework. In a truly circular system, efforts are made to minimize or eliminate unrecoverable waste. However, when unrecoverable waste is inevitable, it impacts circularity by creating a linear disposal path. To address this challenge, emphasis should be placed on designing products with recyclability, reusability, compostability or energy valorisation in mind.

Formula that describes the Unrecoverable Waste is defined below:

$$W = W_0 + \frac{W_F + W_C}{2} \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

$$W_0 = M(1 - C_R - C_U - C_C - C_E) \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

$$W_F = M \frac{(1 - E_F)F_R}{E_F} \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

$$W_C = M(1 - E_C)C_R \quad \text{Equation 11}$$

Where,

W = Mass of unrecoverable waste associated with a product.

W_0 = Mass of unrecoverable waste through a product's material going into landfill, waste to energy and any other type of process where the materials are no longer recoverable.

W_F = Mass of unrecoverable waste generated when producing recycled feedstock for a product.

W_C = Mass of unrecoverable waste generated in the process of recycling parts of a product.

C_R = Fraction of mass of a product being collected to go into a recycling process.

C_U = Fraction of mass of a product going into component reuse.

C_C = Fraction of mass of a product being collected to go into a composting process.

C_E = Fraction of mass of a product being collected for energy recovery where the material satisfies the requirements for inclusion.

E_F = Efficiency of the recycling process used to produce recycled feedstock for a product.

F_R = Fraction of mass of a product's feedstock from recycled sources.

E_C = Efficiency of the recycling process used for the portion of a product collected for recycling.

C_R = Fraction of mass of a product being collected to go into a recycling process.

Linear Flow Index

In a general circular economy context, the term "Linear Flow" refers to the linear model of resource consumption, where materials are extracted, used to make products, and then disposed of as waste.

The Linear Flow Index (LFI) can potentially measure the degree to which a system follows this linear model.

The formula used to represent the LFI is the following:

$$LFI = \frac{V + W}{2M + \frac{W_F - W_C}{2}} \quad \text{Equation 12}$$

It is assumed that $W_F = W_C = 1$ so:

$$LFI = \frac{V + W}{2M} \quad \text{Equation 13}$$

Utility

The Utility (X) is integrated in the MCI with two components: the length of the product's use phase (lifespan) and the intensity of use (functional units).

For the calculation of both lifespan and intensity, there must be a reference process (monoculture) to be compared with the scenario proposed (IMTA). Then the formula below shows the circularity improvement of our production system based on the average or the baseline described.

$$X = \left(\frac{L}{L_{av}}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{U}{U_{av}}\right) \quad \text{Equation 14}$$

Where,

L = Actual average lifetime of an infrastructure element.

L_{av} = Average lifetime of an industry-average infrastructure element of the same type.

U = Actual average number of functional units (kg of biomass harvested) achieved during the use phase of an infrastructure element.

U_{av} = Average number of functional units (kg of biomass harvested) achieved during the use phase of an industry-average infrastructure element of the same type.

Material Circularity Indicator

The material Circularity Indicator (MCI) integrates the previous indicators, taking into account the virgin feedstock and the unrecoverable infrastructure elements waste as part of the Linear Flow Index, together with the utility. The formula is described as follows:

$$MCI = 1 - LFI \cdot F(X) \quad \text{Equation 15}$$

By applying the utility factor $F(X) = \frac{0.9}{X}$, the value 0.1 represents a fully linear product, and it will increase until 1 for the maximal circularity.

4 Circularity assessment

4.1 IMTA Lab Ireland

The research on this IMTA-lab, managed by Marine Institute, was focused on multi-trophic production involving salmon (*Salmo salar*), seaweeds (*Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima*), sea urchin (*Paracentrotus lividus*), and oyster (*Ostrea edulis*). **Figure 5** shows the Lab configuration located in Bertraghboy Bay (Ireland).

Figure 5. IMTA Lab Ireland design

Emissions from salmon, particularly rich in nitrogen and phosphorus, become a valuable resource for extractive species. Seaweeds were cultivated to absorb and utilize the inorganic nutrients, contributing to the improvement of the water quality and to their own biomass production. Simultaneously, sea urchins and oysters were integrated into the system. Sea urchins were grown using the seaweeds produced on site, while oysters act as filter feeders, removing particulate organic matter and enhancing also water quality. Their presence complements the nutrient cycling process and further contributes to maintaining a balanced ecosystem. For a better understanding of nutrient bioremediation flows, the next diagram was elaborated for this lab (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Bioremediation in IMTA-lab Ireland

Circularity assessment of Ireland IMTA-lab focused on the evaluation of the experimental trial, with a production of 50 t FW/y of salmon, 2.1 t FW/y of seaweeds, 75.6 kg FW/y of oysters and 64 kg FW/y of sea urchins.

4.1.1 Results IMTA Lab Ireland

Nutrient management

The bioremediation indicator was calculated through the evaluation of nutrient emissions from salmon, which were differentiated between dissolved and particulate matter. Table 1 shows the nutrient balance obtained from this Lab, in which seaweeds mitigated the emissions of the dissolved nutrient fraction, oysters absorbed particulate nutrient fractions, and sea urchins utilized the seaweed grown on-site. Information on the excretion and respiration of the low-trophic animals was not available and therefore excluded from the analysis.

Table 1 Nutrient balance in the Irish IMTA lab (all values refer to 1 kg of biomass—WWT).

Nutrients (kg)	Emitted	Absorbed			
	Salmon	<i>Alaria</i>	<i>Saccharina</i>	Oyster	Urchin
Dissolved N	7.18×10^{-2}	1.40×10^{-4}	8.05×10^{-5}	-	-
Dissolved P	1.82×10^{-2}	1.97×10^{-4}	1.97×10^{-4}	-	-
Dissolved C	1.14×10^{-2}	1.77×10^{-3}	1.28×10^{-3}	-	-
Particulate N	5.57×10^{-3}	-	-	1.12×10^{-6}	1.89×10^{-5}
Particulate P	1.03×10^{-1}	-	-	2.99×10^{-6}	1.89×10^{-6}
Particulate C	1.82×10^{-2}	-	-	6.40×10^{-5}	1.08×10^{-4}

Salmon nutrient emissions were calculated in accordance with the approach developed by Wang *et al.* (2011), that enables the estimation of N, P and C emissions to water from the fish feeding¹¹. N and P assimilated by seaweeds were estimated from elementary analysis, while C was calculated in accordance with literature⁵⁴, considering the carbon fixation and storage potential of macroalgae. The N and P taken up by oysters were estimated based on nutritional analyses, while C was calculated from nutrient assimilation efficiencies in IMTA⁵⁴. The same reference (Nederlof *et al.* 2022) was used to estimate N, P and C absorption by sea urchins, which was based on the theoretical assimilation efficiency.

Resource use efficiency

Fuel consumption refers to the petrol needed for maintenance and harvesting activities in both the monoculture and IMTA scenarios. Derived from the LCA study (Deliverable 4.3), energy within petrol consumption in the monoculture scenario was 2.53E-01 kWh/kg of biomass harvested, whereas the energy within the fuel consumed in IMTA conditions was reduced (2.52E-01 kWh/kg of biomass harvested).

Regarding materials embedded in infrastructure elements, D4.3 also allowed the identification of steel, concrete and wood as the main materials used in the farm. Total materials involved in the monoculture scenario was 0.04 kg of materials per kg of biomass harvested, while 0.05 kg of materials was used per kg of biomass harvested in IMTA.

Table 2. Circularity results IMTA Lab Ireland shows the results obtained from the IMTA in Ireland. The calculation of FCR and linearity indicators were not calculated as no actions were taken to improve circularity in that sense. Water indicator was unable to be calculated in an open system.

Table 2. Circularity results IMTA Lab Ireland (% of circularity improvement compared to monoculture conditions)

Pillar	Indicator	Result
Use of resources	Energy	0.38%
Nutrient management	N bioremediation	7.71%
	P bioremediation	12.08%
	C bioremediation	2.63%

4.2 IMTA Lab Brazil

This IMTA lab was carried out by the Federal University of Rio Grande (FURG), located in the city of Rio Grande in Brazil, with biofloc technology (BFT), focused on the optimization of white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) production in a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) (Figure 7).

Figure 7. IMTA lab Brazil design

The BFT entails the cultivation of dense populations of microorganisms in the water, creating a dynamic environment where the nitrogen excreted by fed species is converted into microorganism biomass (biofloc) under aeration and carbon fertilization. By active carbon addition (molasses) and constant aeration, the biofloc growth is stimulated.

The experiments carried out by this lab aimed at determining the most effective biomass ratios among marine white shrimp, tilapia and algae, particularly evaluating the impacts of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and sea lettuce (*Ulva lactuca*) in regulating organic material and inorganic nutrients. Moreover, the lab tested the performance of the system when fish meal was substituted by a fish meal analogue (FMA) in the shrimp diet formulation. The FMA used in this study was developed by Guabi Nutrition and Animal Health S.A. and consisted of a balanced blend of terrestrial animal coproducts supplemented with amino acids, minerals, and commercial vitamins. The animals were fed 2 times a day with the isoprotein and isoenergetic diets (feed pellets with 38% crude protein and 7% lipids) and FMA with a 50/50 ratio.

This IMTA system was designed to maximize the efficiency of nutrient utilization and circularity within the system^{55 56}. White shrimp served as the primary species⁵⁷ and produce organic emissions and nutrients as coproducts of their metabolic processes. These nutrients include nitrogenous and phosphorylated compounds. Nutrient-rich water was recirculated between the shrimp, tilapia and seaweed tanks. Tilapia is a marketable species capable of consuming bioflocs and *Ulva* absorbs dissolved nutrients, including nitrogen and phosphorus, from water contributing to overall nutrient balance⁵⁸. This not only aids in water quality management but also provides an additional valuable product, seaweeds, that can be harvested and used as nutrient-rich supplements for aquaculture feed⁵⁹.

The IMTA lab circularity assessment was focused on the evaluation of the experimental trial, with a production of 4.3 kg/m³ FW of shrimps, 13.4 kg/m³ FW of tilapia and 2 kg/m³ FW of seaweeds.

4.2.1 Results IMTA Lab Brazil

Nutrient management

Bioremediation was calculated with data from monitoring water flow and information on nutrient concentrations for one year covering three production cycles for shrimp, two production cycles for tilapia and four production cycles for seaweed. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the shrimp, tilapia and seaweed tanks were used to estimate the bioremediation potential for N and P. In the shrimp tank, levels of ammonia, nitrate, nitrite and phosphate increased due to the metabolic processes, while Total Suspended Solids (TSS) increased due to the biofloc formation. The tilapia tank showed a similar pattern, where ammonia, nitrite, nitrate and phosphate concentrations increased due to the biological outcomes of the nutrient assimilation of the fish, but the TSS decreased due to the capability of tilapia to eat the biofloc generated in the previous tank. Finally, the seaweed tank showed the process of nutrient bioremediation with decreasing levels of dissolved ammonia, nitrite, nitrate and phosphate; TSS decreased due to the biological structure of *Ulva*, that retains part of the biofloc in the tank and is removed. Full data of monitoring period are included in the open-access publication derived from this work (Checa *et al.*, 2024).

Resource use efficiency

For shrimp monoculture, the FCR was 1.75⁶⁰, while it was decreased to 1.34 in the BFT system with tilapia⁶¹. For tilapia monoculture, FCR was 1.75⁶⁰, improving to 0.85, as was reported by Poersch *et al.*⁶¹, in the BFT system. Therefore, FCR of shrimp and tilapia was improved in BFT system in comparison to conventional farms⁶⁰, leading to increase resource use efficiency in terms of feed.

Moreover, the substitution of fish meal in the conventional feed by poultry industry coproduct in the shrimp diet implied a decrease of the linearity on the feed. Particularly, system performance was not affected when fish meal was replaced by 50 and 100% FMA. This strategy had a direct implication on the circularity performance since the shrimp production reduced the dependency on new resources.

In terms of energy use, BFT systems imply the aeration of culture tanks to ensure homogeneous distribution of nutrients and biofloc, while avoiding biofloc deposition. The BFT aeration equipment increases energy demand compared to a pond system (baseline of this study), therefore energy consumption is a disadvantage of BFT⁶². On the other hand, when BFT is compared in both monoculture and IMTA scenarios, the relative energy demand regarding the biomass culture could be potentially interpreted as an improvement regarding the resource use efficiency.

To address circularity of infrastructure materials, kg of materials per kg of the biomass harvested was compared between monoculture and IMTA scenarios. To do so, components and elements identified

in the LCA study⁶³ were taken as the basis for the indicator. For monoculture condition, 1.01 kg of materials per kg of biomass harvested was estimated, while the same indicator for BFT scenario resulted in 0.37 kg of materials per kg of biomass harvested. Results obtained from IMTA Lab Brazil are shown in

Table 3. Energy indicator is not represented as no circularity improvement was shown, and C bioremediation was not calculated due to lack of information.

Table 3. Circularity results IMTA Lab Brazil (% of circularity improvement compared to monoculture conditions)

Pillar	Indicator	Result
Use of resources	Feed- FCR	37%
	Feed- Linearity	50%
	Water	99.68%
	Infrastructure	63.30%
Nutrient management	N bioremediation	22.34%
	P bioremediation	75.61%

4.3 IMTA Lab South Africa

IMTA Lab South Africa was studied under a circularity perspective focusing on 2 trials. The first trial took place in a fully commercial integrated abalone-*Ulva* system at Buffeljags Abalone farm. The farm is managed by Viking Aquaculture and is located approximately 200 km east of Cape Town on a pristine stretch of coastal ground near the remote settlement of Buffeljags on the Cape south coast. The second trial took place in a sea urchin-*Ulva* pilot-commercial scale experimental system on the same farm.

The abalone (*Haliotis midae*)-*Ulva lacunculata* IMTA system consists of seven modular platforms, each comprising four clusters. The present study addressed each cluster that was composed of a 150 m³ D-ended *Ulva* paddle-raceway and multiple abalone tanks (each 8.5 m³) arranged in six rows, with each row housing seven abalone raceway tanks. The effluent water from the abalone tanks in each cluster flowed into the adjacent *Ulva* paddle-raceway. The feeding regime for an abalone monoculture production system consisted of formulated feed for 4 days and wild harvested kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*) for 3 days per week. Since the green seaweed *Ulva* is known for its potential to take up nutrients from the environment, N and P from abalone tanks is bioremediated by the seaweed⁶⁴. A continuous circulation of seawater through these tanks and *Ulva* paddle-raceways ensured a steady supply of cool and aerated water for the growing abalone. Experiments in the SA IMTA-lab were carried out to

monitor the physical and chemical parameters of the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA system with increasing (50, 75 and 100%) recirculation rates²⁹.

Operating independently, but at the same farm, the second trial consisted of an integrated urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*)-*Ulva lacunculata* system that consisted of 5 8000 L glass fiber tanks, linked to a 14000 L *Ulva* paddle-raceway and a 14000 L sump. In monoculture, sea urchins' diet comprised a combination of formulated feed (pellets) containing 20% DW *Ulva*, providing a well-rounded nutritional intake⁶⁵ in addition to freshly harvested farmed *Ulva*.

Effluent water from each of the sea urchin tanks was directed into the *Ulva* paddle-raceway (where nutrients were reduced by bioremediation of the seaweed), having passed through the drum-filter for the removal of larger particulates. For a better understanding of nutrient bioremediation flows in both systems, abalone and sea urchin, the below nutrient flow diagrams were elaborated (*Figure 8*)

Figure 8. Bioremediation in IMTA-labs South Africa -a) abalone system b) urchin system

4.3.1 Results IMTA Lab South Africa (abalone system)

Nutrient management

Regarding the abalone system, bioremediation was calculated based on the information on Total Ammonia Nitrogen (TAN), nitrate, nitrite and phosphate concentrations in the inlet flow in *Ulva* raceway that were compared to concentrations in the effluent water from abalone raceways⁶⁶. Data were sourced from Geldart, 2022⁶⁷ who studied nutrient fluctuations in the system operating at 50%, 75% recirculation, as well as at 100% recirculation for a short-term. Full data from this monitoring are presented in the open-access publication derived from this work (Checa *et al.* 2024).

Resource use efficiency

When implementing the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA system, the feed regime was similar to monoculture, but the wild harvested kelp was substituted whenever IMTA grown *Ulva lacunculata* was available. This means that the formulated feed was provided for 4 days out of the week, while wild harvested kelp

was provided for 1 day and IMTA grown *Ulva lacinulata* was fed for 2 days per week. This feeding regime was assumed for the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA system for the purpose of this comparative analysis; however, it should be noted that in practice the choice of seaweed is dependent on what is available at the time.

Combining the feeding regime with the specific FCR related to the different feed types, the FCR for the abalone monoculture system was 6.16; when the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA system was implemented, the FCR was reduced to 4.01. Uneaten fractions also decreased from 1.14% to 0.71%, while the linearity of the feed decreases from 100% (no ingredient sourced from valorisation routes) for the abalone monoculture system to a linearity of 71.42% for the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA system.

Results from abalone system are presented in **Table 4**. Infrastructure and C bioremediation indicators were not calculated due to lack of information.

Table 4. Circularity results IMTA SA abalone-*Ulva* (% of circularity improvement compared to monoculture conditions)

Pillar	Indicator	Result
Use of resources	Feed- FCR	34.90%
	Feed- Linearity	28.58%
	Water	50.00%
	Energy	34.30%
Nutrient management	N bioremediation	18.17%
	P bioremediation	6.01%

In terms of water use, 50% water recirculation at Buffeljags abalone farm played a key role in enhancing the circularity of the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA system, as it allowed for a significant reduction in the reliance on fresh incoming seawater from the adjacent ocean. This promotes resource efficiency as the system recirculates a substantial portion of the water, minimizing the demand for external resources.

Moreover, the reduced dependence on pumping of fresh seawater contributes to energy efficiency. Recirculating 50% of the water in the system, enabled by the bioremediation (ammonia removal) capacity of *Ulva*, minimizes the energy expenditure associated with bringing in new seawater. Energy consumed in abalone monoculture conditions was 10.35 kWh per ton of biomass harvested, but when IMTA conditions were implemented the energy consumption was reduced to 6.80 kWh per ton of biomass harvested.

4.3.2 Results IMTA Lab South Africa (sea urchin system)

Nutrient management

In relation to the sea urchin system, N emissions were calculated based on feed nutritional values, performing the nutrient balance from proteins provided in feed to N retained by sea urchin. Live sea urchins (9.5 t) were fed with a pelleted formulated feed at 1.5% body weight (BW) per day for 4 days a week over the entire 7-month production cycle. During the IMTA scenario, sea urchins were fed fresh *Ulva* at 6% BW per day three times a week for the first 4-months and with pellets at 1.5% BW per day for 4 days a week for the remaining 3-months of the production cycle. In monoculture conditions, 17.08 t of formulated feed per production cycle were provided, with a total of 257 g of proteins per kg of feed, resulting in 0.70 t DIN per production cycle with the 0.16 protein to N conversion factor. Considering sea urchin potential N retention of 10.52%, approximately 0.63 t DIN remains in the system. Dissolved N bio-available in water was 60%, so the total N not retained by urchins was 0.38 t of N per production cycle.

Ulva supplied for urchin feeding over the production cycle was 68.31 t (WW) per IMTA production cycle, and the N within *Ulva* was 0.27 t per IMTA production cycle. The total amount of formulated feed provided was 7.32 t per IMTA production cycle, equating to 0.32 t of N provided by formulated feed per IMTA production cycle. Therefore, N supplied from feed was 0.59 t of N per IMTA production cycle. DIN uptake efficiency of *Ulva* was 80%, so the N retained by *Ulva* was 0.25 t, and the N not retained was 0.064 t of N per IMTA production cycle.

Resource use efficiency

In terms of feed, FCR for formulated feed in monoculture was 0.4, and the FCR related to the IMTA conditions was 0.91. The uneaten feed was 2% for monoculture, and 1.14% for IMTA. The linearity of the feed was reduced from 80% in the monoculture conditions to 34.3% when implementing IMTA.

Regarding water use, implementing a high level of seawater recirculation (90%) in a sea urchin-*Ulva* IMTA system offered notable benefits in terms of water conservation of fresh seawater resources, being crucial for sustainable aquaculture.

With 90% seawater recirculation, the need for pumping large volumes of seawater from external sources was minimised. This reduction in water exchange led to lower pumping energy requirements, contributing to overall energy savings. Energy consumption for sea urchin monoculture conditions was 12.45 kWh/t of biomass harvested, and 3.54 kWh in the sea urchin-*Ulva* IMTA system.

Regarding resources use indicator, infrastructure elements (*Ulva* D-Shaped paddle raceway, pipes and fittings, pumps, baskets, among others) were identified as part of the SA IMTA-lab LCA study⁶³. Monoculture and IMTA scenarios were compared considering the infrastructure materials weight per

kg of biomass harvested, resulting in 1.26 kg of material per kg of biomass harvested in monoculture and 0.42 kg of material per kg of biomass harvested in IMTA scenario.

Table 5 shows the results of sea urchin-*Ulva* system. FCR indicator is not represented in the table since no circularity improvement was found; P and C bioremediation indicators were not calculated due to lack of information.

Table 5. Circularity results IMTA SA- sea urchin-*Ulva* (% of circularity improvement compared to monoculture conditions)

Pillar	Indicator	Result
Use of resources	Feed- Linearity	57.13%
	Water	90.00%
	Energy	71.57%
	Infrastructure	66.67%
Nutrient management	N bioremediation	80.00%

4.4 IMTA Lab Scotland

The Scotland IMTA lab 'Port-a-Bhuiltin' (PaB) is an experimental low-trophic aquaculture (LTA) site located 200 m off the mainland shore in the Firth of Lorn-Loch Linnhe estuarine system, on the west coast of Scotland (56° 29.176 N, 5° 28.315 W). Since 2014, this site has functioned as an experimental seaweed cultivation area managed by the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS). Marine Scotland has granted a license for seaweed cultivation at the site, and with a subsequent update in 2020, the license was extended to include the experimental non-commercial co-cultivation of selected shellfish species. Being a research site, cultivated species and production scales vary from year to year depending on various research project interests and requirements, but have focussed mainly on the cultivation of kelps (*A. esculenta*, *S. latissima*) and European flat oysters (*O. edulis*). Within the ASTRAL project, additional species were trialled including the red seaweed dulse (*Palmaria palmata*), king scallops (*P. maximus*) and sea urchins (*E. esculentus*). The layout for IMTA lab Scotland is shown in [Figure 9](#).

Figure 9 Layout of IMTA system in IMTA lab Scotland. Top: full site layout, showing seaweed and shellfish growing lines. Bottom: shellfish cultivation system with floating oyster baskets and hanging nestier trays (for scallop cultivation).

As presented in the methodology chapter, the evaluation of the bioremediation pillar was not applicable in IMTA lab Scotland as it did not deploy fed-species. However, we identified as a potential case study to evaluate the efficiency in terms of infrastructure management when additional low trophic species were added to the baseline conditions (macroalgae cultivation). Therefore, we selected this IMTA lab to evaluate the MCI indicator that was calculated and compared between three scenarios (Table 6).

Table 6. Summary of scenarios.

Scenario IMTA Lab Scotland	Species	Circularity Strategy
Scenario 1 (Monoculture)	Only seaweed (<i>Alaria esculenta</i> , <i>Saccharina latissima</i>)	Not applicable
Scenario 2 (LTA)	Scenario 1 + bivalve molluscs (<i>Ostrea edulis</i> , <i>Pecten maximus</i>)	Synergies on infrastructure (same moorings and buoyancy elements)
Scenario 3 (LTA-improved)	Scenario 1 + bivalve molluscs (<i>Ostrea edulis</i> , <i>Pecten maximus</i>)	Same as scenario 2 + substitution by coconut bio-based ropes

Scenario 1 and scenario 2 were implemented during the Scotland IMTA lab operation, but scenario 3 is a theoretical scenario. The substitution of polysteel longlines with coconut bio-based³ ropes for seaweed production offers a sustainable alternative, leveraging renewable coconut fibres that are biodegradable.

4.4.1 Results IMTA Lab Scotland

Monoculture scenario

Monoculture scenario infrastructure elements were sourced as virgin material from the virgin feedstock perspective for almost all the infrastructure components. Only corroded steel weights were completely reused; 75% of polysteel seaweed growing lines were reused incorporating virgin materials whenever the reutilisation was not possible; 50% of plastic boxes for harvesting were reused, 25% came from recycled process and 25% from virgin materials.

From a waste perspective, no infrastructure material was collected for composting (C_c) or energy recovery (C_e); fraction of mass collected for recycling (C_r) and reuse (C_u) are shown in Annex Table 1. No waste generated during the recycling process (W_f) was considered, and the recycling efficiency was considered as 100% (E_c and E_f). Total production (U) for baseline scenario was 31,584 kg of biomass harvested, the same value as the reference (U_{Av}).

Virgin feedstock indicator showed that from a total mass of 9,501.60 kg of infrastructure materials needed in IMTA lab Scotland, 8,575.43 kg were sourced from virgin materials. Total unrecoverable waste during the life cycle of the materials (from gate to gate) were 6,471.31 kg. With a linearity factor of 0.83 in the Linear Flow Index, a utility factor of 1 and a total of 0.25 in the Material Circularity Indicator. Detailed results obtained from monoculture conditions are shown in Annex Table 1.

LTA scenario

LTA scenario infrastructure elements were sourced as virgin material from the virgin feedstock perspective for almost all the infrastructure components, as mentioned above. High-Density Polyethylene lantern baskets for King scallop cultivation was totally reutilised.

From a waste perspective, no material was collected for composting (C_c) and energy recovery (C_e); fraction of mass collected for recycling (C_r) and reuse (C_u) are shown in Annex Table 2. No waste generated during the recycling process (W_f) was considered, and the recycle efficiency was considered as 100% (E_c and E_f). Total production (U) for LTA scenario was 34,395.6 kg of biomass harvested, and the production of reference (U_{Av}) was 31,584 kg, the monoculture biomass harvested.

³ Bio-based products are wholly or partly derived from materials of biological origin

Virgin feedstock indicator showed that from a total mass of 12,175.876 kg of infrastructure materials needed in IMTA lab Scotland, 10,290.504 kg were sourced from virgin materials. Total unrecoverable waste during the life cycle of the materials (from gate to gate) were 6,657.088 kg. With a linearity factor of 0.787 in the Linear Flow Index, a utility factor of 1.089 and a total of 0.349 in the Material Circularity Indicator. Detailed results obtained in this scenario are shown in Annex Table 2.

LTA improved scenario

LTA improved scenario infrastructure elements were sourced as virgin material from the virgin feedstock perspective for almost all the infrastructure components, as mentioned above. High-Density Polyethylene lantern baskets for King scallop cultivation was totally reutilised. Seaweed growing lines were substituted by coconut fibre longlines classified as bio-based material (F_s).

From a waste perspective, coconut fibre seaweed longline were collected for composting (C_c), no materials were collected for energy recovery (C_e); fraction of mass collected for recycling (C_r) and reuse (C_u) are shown in Annex Table 3 Scotland IMTA-lab LTA improved scenario MCI results No waste generated during the recycling process (W_f) was considered, and the recycle efficiency was considered as 100% (E_c and E_f). Total production (U) for LTA improved scenario was 34,395.6 kg of biomass harvested, and the production of reference (U_{AV}) was 31,584 kg, the monoculture biomass harvested. The LTA improved scenario implemented one specific improvement within the production system, the substitution of polysteel seaweed longlines with bio-based materials reducing the specific performance in terms of circularity of this concrete infrastructure element: kg of material needed (M) were reduced by 89.39%; the Virgin feedstock (V) and Unrecoverable waste were totally reduced, and the Linear Flow Index went from 0.25 to 0. The only value negatively affected was the Utility (X), that was reduced by 56.44% due to the lifespan reduction from 2.5 years to 1 year, but despite of that, Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) was improved by 29.03% overall.

Virgin feedstock indicator showed that from a total mass of 12,042.772 kg of infrastructure materials needed in Scotland IMTA-lab, 10,253.280 kg were sourced from virgin materials. Total unrecoverable waste during the life cycle of the materials (from gate to gate) were 6,619.864 kg. The linearity factor was 0.780 in the Linear Flow Index, the utility factor was 1.071 and the total Material Circularity Indicator was 0.355. Detailed results obtained in this scenario are shown in Annex Table 3.

Comparison

Total kg of materials needed for each LTA scenario increase as additional species were incorporated into the production system, requiring more infrastructure elements like baskets, ropes, floats and minor elements, but other elements like moorings and weights were not added. In that sense, the kg of materials required for LTA scenario and LTA improved scenario in comparison with monoculture scenario increased by 28.15%, and 26.74%, respectively.

Total unrecoverable waste was calculated and compared between each scenario. As shown in Figure 10, virgin feedstock represents 90.25% for monoculture scenario, and it was similar in LTA and LTA improved scenarios (84.52% and 85.14%, respectively). The small difference for LTA improved scenario is linked to the reduction on the total kg of materials related to the polysteel longline substitution with the bio-based materials.

Figure 10. Percentage of V and W in relation to M

In terms of Linear Flow Index, Utility Factor and Material Circularity Indicator, results are shown in Figure 11. The LFI decreased for LTA and LTA improved scenarios (5.54% and 6.35%, respectively) while the Utility Factor increased 8.90% for LTA scenario and 7.14% for LTA improved scenario. Finally, the MCI increased by 39.79% for LTA scenario and by 42.02% for LTA improved scenario. Thus, both LTA and LTA improved scenarios were better than the baseline scenario (LFI were reduced while Utility and MCI were increased)..

Figure 11. LFI, X and MCI comparison between scenarios

5 Discussion

The present work provides an assessment based on single-focus indicators to evaluate the level of implementation of circular economy strategies⁶⁸. Following Linder *et al.* (2017) recommendations, metrics for circularity assessment at production level were quantified through measuring flows as single attributes, instead of providing information of the entire environmental profile or the performance on the value chain⁴⁰.

In addition to the intrinsic circularity of IMTA (nutrient recirculation), this work provides the evaluation of the resource use efficiency as it is recognized as a second fundamental pillar supporting the circularity of IMTA systems. The indicators defined were applied for the evaluation of 4 IMTA labs that were compared with monoculture conditions.

For a better interpretation of the results, a ranking system was developed to easily visualize the main circular attributes of each IMTA lab.

Table 7 shows that IMTA Lab Ireland best improvement due to IMTA was in the area of P bioremediation (12.08%) compared to the monoculture scenario. Regarding IMTA Lab Brazil, water recirculation was the indicator that improved most (99.68%), followed by the bioremediation effects achieved by the extractive species (75.61% for P bioremediation). The abalone - Ulva system in IMTA Lab South Africa improved circularity (50.00%) mostly due to the increase in water recirculation rates and due to the reduction in the FCR (34.90%). Finally, the sea urchin - Ulva IMTA system in IMTA Lab South Africa improved circularity mostly in term of water recirculation (90%) and N bioremediation (80%).

As explained in the Methodology section, IMTA Lab Scotland was studied through MCI to evaluate in detail the infrastructure circularity. Improvement along the different scenarios was evidenced by the MCI improving by 39.79% and 42.02% in the LTA and LTA-improved scenarios, respectively.

Table 7. Circularity assessment-ranking system

	RESOURCE USE EFFICIENCY					NUNTRIENT MANAGEMENT		
	FCR formulated feed	Linearity	Water	Energy	Infrastructure	N Bioremediation	P Bioremediation	C Bioremediation
Ireland IMTA lab								
Brazil IMTA lab								
SA IMTA lab (abalone)								
SA IMTA lab (sea urchin)								

Table legend	No information available		
	Not applicable		
	Circularity is not improved compared to monoculture		
	Circularity ranking:		
	Low performance	Medium performance	High performance

6 Conclusions

The ASTRAL circularity assessment was initially conducted through the harmonization of the concepts sourced from literature with respect to the definition of circular economy and its application to aquaculture. A framework, based on circularity-evidence metrics, was, then, developed to encourage IMTA and general aquaculture producers to measure and control the circularity performance of seafood farming.

In addition to bioremediation indicators, complementary metrics were applied to IMTA to quantify the level of implementation in terms of resource use efficiency strategies, which further ensured the alignment of these systems with circular economy.

Results confirmed that IMTA systems perform in line with circular attributes embedded in the definition of nutrient bioremediation. Metrics on bioremediation would promote standardization of nutrient recycling rates, from which the effectiveness of the systems could be evaluated. In terms of resource use, the present assessment identified improvements in water recirculation and energy efficiency as being indicators of the economic benefits and higher resilience of IMTA systems. Moreover, the present assessment allowed the quantification of benefits in terms of feeding due to the reduction of linear ingredients in the feed formulation and improved FCR.

Regarding infrastructure (capital goods), the present study addressed the lifespan as a fundamental parameter that should be considered in the circularity assessment. Generally, better maintenance or the substitution of infrastructure elements with increased durability would increase the functionality and thus the circularity. Infrastructure was studied in the circularity assessment through the MCI analysed and compared between three scenarios (baseline, LTA and LTA improved). The integration of additional species into the monoculture system (LTA scenario) shown a better circularity performance as the utility factor was increased by the increased biomass harvested with a few new structure elements required. Results confirmed that the MCI increased for LTA improved scenario, in which the theoretical substitution of polysteel lines for seaweed cultivation with coconut fibre ropes, as bio-based material, decreased the unrecoverable waste and the virgin material.

In addition to this assessment, the collaborative work between WPs in ASTRAL evidenced that increasing the level of circularity in seafood value chains requires a multidisciplinary and holistic approach for implementation .

7 Policy recommendations

As part of the synergies actions, ASTRAL and iFishIENCI projects worked together, among other EU projects, on a policy recommendation document for a more circular aquaculture approach. While

ASTRAL project was starting its implementation when the policy recommendations were elaborated, we worked together for the integration of the IMTA concept and perspectives within the recommendations.

Particularly, this document provides suggestions regarding the following aspects:

- Definition of circular aquaculture,
- Methodologies for measuring circularity,
- Improving circularity, and
- Encouraging sectorial and cross-sectorial co-governance.

From the ASTRAL project, we collaborated for the integration of the multi-trophic aspects through the following recommendations, highlighted in green in the next figure:

Figure 12: Main ASTRAL contributions to the “Policy recommendations for a more circular aquaculture”.

On the other hand, and as it is reflected in D7.7, the importance of enhancing cross-sectorial and co-governance approaches lies in the necessity of reviewing and updating legislation to avoid potential contradictions at national, regional, and local levels. In addition, further cooperation among diverse stakeholders must be pursued, not only to create a broader knowledge network, but also to introduce participatory approaches in decision-making procedures in which all stakeholders are able to actively participate. The document D7.7 also highlighted the need of promoting the proper use of concepts in relation to IMTA practices. Consequently, the present deliverable incorporates the concept of coproduct to replace the term “waste or byproduct”.

8 Scientific paper

The present work is part of the recent paper by Checa *et al.* published in the journal *Fishes* (special issue on IMTA) and titled «Circularity Assessment in Aquaculture: The Case of Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) Systems».

Figure 13: ASTRAL Open-access publication on Circularity Assessment in Aquaculture.

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Annex: IMTA-Lab Scotland MCI results

Annex Table 1. Scotland IMTA-lab baseline scenario MCI results

INFRASTRUCTURE				Virgin feedstock	Waste				Linearity	Utility			Material Circularity Indicator		
	Material Type	Unit	Total mass	Mass of virgin material (V)	Unrecoverable waste (W)	Unrecoverable waste (W0)	Fraction of mass collected for recycling (Cr)	Fraction of mass for reuse (Cu)	Linear Flow Index (LFI)	Utility factor (X)	Lifetime (L)	Lifetime average (Lav)	Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)		
Seaweed	Anchor	Galvanised steel	kg	2,400.000	2,400.000	2,400.000	2,400.000	0	0	1	1	10	10	0.1	
	Anchor chain	Steel	kg	1,938.000	1,938.000	969.000	969.000	0	0.5	0.75	1	10	10	0.325	
	Anchor line	Polysteel (32mm)	kg	445.091	445.091	445.091	445.091	0	0	1	1	10	10	0.1	
	Node Ring	Galvanised steel. Cast steel	kg	594.000	594.000	297.000	297.000	0	0.5	0.75	1	5	5	0.325	
	Shackle	Galvanised steel. High tensile steel	kg	43.650	43.650	21.825	21.825	0	0.5	0.75	1	5	5	0.325	
	Grid Line	Polysteel (32mm)	kg	300.436	300.436	300.436	300.436	0	0	1	1	8	8	0.1	
	Trawl Float	HDPE	kg	180.000	180.000	90.000	90.000	0	0.5	0.75	1	10	10	0.325	
	Grid Riser Rope + Extension Arm	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	40.392	40.392	40.392	40.392	0	0	1	1	2	2	0.1	
	Double Figure 8 Through Trawl Float	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	11.880	11.880	11.880	11.880	0	0	1	1	2	2	0.1	
	Prusik knot (Grid-Riser Connection)	Nylon braided (6mm)	kg	2.448	2.448	2.448	2.448	0	0	1	1	2	2	0.1	
	Rope riser to cushion buoy	Polysteel (32mm)	kg	18.545	18.545	18.545	18.545	0	0	1	1	2	2	0.1	
	Cushion Buoy	Polystyrene filling	kg	40.000	40.000	40.000	40.000	0	0	1	1	8	8	0.1	
		Polyethylene shell (8mm thick)	kg	240.000	240.000	240.000	240.000	0	0	1	1	8	8	0.1	
	Surface Buoyancy (temporary growing structures)	Cushion Buoy Steel work (incl. shackles, pins, etc.)	Shackle: galvanised steel pins: galvanised steel	kg	200.000	200.000	100.000	100.000	0	0.5	0.75	1	3	3	0.325
	Cultivation materials (temporary)	Polyform Pencil Buoys	Plastic (soft vinyl)	kg	108.000	108.000	27.000	27.000	0	0.75	0.625	1	5	5	0.4375
Weights		corroded steel	kg	72.000	0.000	36.000	36.000	0	0.5	0.25	1	10	10	0.775	
	Riser	Nylon (6mm)	kg	11.178	11.178	11.178	11.178	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.1	
	Seaweed growing lines	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	148.896	37.224	37.224	37.224	0	0.75	0.25	1	2.5	2.5	0.775	
	Harvest Boxes	Plastic base. Recyclable walls	kg	990.000	247.500	0.000	0.000	0.5	0.5	0.125	1	5	5	0.8875	

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growing structures)	Twine	Polyester	kg	2.031	2.031	2.031	2.031	0	0	1	1	1	1	0.1
		HDPE	kg	85.600	85.600	85.600	85.600	0	0	1	1	20	20	0.1
Site markings	Special mark buoys	Polyurethene	kg	40.920	40.920	40.920	40.920	0	0	1	1	20	20	0.1
		Galvanised Steel	kg	20.940	20.940	20.940	20.940	0	0	1	1	20	20	0.1
		Anchors for special mark	Steel	kg	300.000	300.000	300.000	300.000	0	0	1	1	10	10
	Chain	Steel	kg	665.000	665.000	332.500	332.500	0	0.5	0.75	1	10	10	0.325
	Shackles	Galvanised steel	kg	2.600	2.600	1.300	1.300	0	0.5	0.75	1	5	5	0.325
	Ballasts	Steel	kg	600.000	600.000	600.000	600.000	0	0	1	1	20	20	0.1
	TOTAL		kg	9,501.607	8,575.435	6,471.310	6,471.310			0.833	1			0.25

Annex Table 2 Scotland IMTA-lab LTA scenario MCI results

				Virgin feedstock	Waste				Linearity	Utility			Material Circularity Indicator	
INFRASTRUCTURE	Material Type	Unit	Total mass	Mass of virgin material (V)	Unrecoverable waste (W)	Unrecoverable waste (W0)	Fraction of mass collected for recycling (Cr)	Fraction of mass for reuse (Cu)	Linear Flow Index (LFI)	Utility factor (X)	Lifetime (L)	Lifetime average (Lav)	Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)	
Moorings	Anchor	Galvanised steel	kg	2,400.000	2,400.000	2,400.000	2,400.000	0	0	1.000	1.089	10	10	0.174
	Anchor chain	Steel	kg	1,938.000	1,938.000	969.000	969.000	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	10	10	0.380
	Anchor line	Polysteel (32mm)	kg	445.091	445.091	445.091	445.091	0	0	1.000	1.089	10	10	0.174
	Node Ring	Galvanised steel. Cast steel	kg	594.000	594.000	297.000	297.000	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	5	5	0.380
	Shackle	Galvanised steel. High tensile steel	kg	43.650	43.650	21.825	21.825	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	5	5	0.380
	Grid Line	Polysteel (32mm)	kg	300.436	300.436	300.436	300.436	0	0	1.000	1.089	8	8	0.174
	Trawl Float	HDPE	kg	180.000	180.000	90.000	90.000	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	10	10	0.380
	Grid Riser Rope + Extension Arm	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	40.392	40.392	40.392	40.392	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174
	Double Figure 8 Through Trawl Float	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	11.880	11.880	11.880	11.880	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174
	Prusik knot (Grid-Riser Connection)	Nylon braided (6mm)	kg	2.448	2.448	2.448	2.448	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174
Seaweed Surface Buoyancy (temporary growing structures) Cultivation materials (temporary growing structures)	Rope riser to cushion buoy	Polysteel (32mm)	kg	18.545	18.545	18.545	18.545	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174
		Polystyrene filling,	kg	40.000	40.000	40.000	40.000	0	0	1.000	1.089	8	8	0.174
	Cushion Buoy	Polyethylene shell (8mm thick)	kg	240.000	240.000	240.000	240.000	0	0	1.000	1.089	8	8	0.174
	Cushion Buoy Steel work (incl. shackles, pins, etc.)	Shackle: galvanised steel Pins: galvanised steel	kg	200.000	200.000	100.000	100.000	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	3	3	0.380
	Polyform Pencil Buoys	Plastic (soft vinyl)	kg	108.000	108.000	27.000	27.000	0	0.75	0.625	1.089	5	5	0.483
	Weights	corroded steel	kg	72.000	0.000	36.000	36.000	0	0.5	0.250	1.089	10	10	0.793
	Riser	Nylon (6mm)	kg	11.178	11.178	11.178	11.178	0	0	1.000	1.089	1	1	0.174
	Seaweed growing lines	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	148.896	37.224	37.224	37.224	0	0.75	0.250	1.089	2.5	2.5	0.793
	Harvest Boxes	Plastic base. Recyclable walls	kg	990.000	247.500	0.000	0.000	0.5	0.5	0.125	1.089	5	5	0.897
	Twine	Polyester	kg	2.031	2.031	2.031	2.031	0	0	1.000	1.089	1	1	0.174

INFRASTRUCTURE				Virgin feedstock	Waste					Linearity	Utility			Material Circularity Indicator
	Material Type	Unit	Total mass	Mass of virgin material (V)	Unrecoverable waste (W)	Unrecoverable waste (W0)	Fraction of mass collected for recycling (Cr)	Fraction of mass for reuse (Cu)	Linear Flow Index (LFI)	Utility factor (X)	Lifetime (L)	Lifetime average (Lav)	Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)	
Special mark buoys	HDPE	kg	85.600	85.600	85.600	85.600	0	0	1.000	1.089	20	20	0.174	
	Polyurethane	kg	40.920	40.920	40.920	40.920	0	0	1.000	1.089	20	20	0.174	
	Galvanised Steel	kg	20.940	20.940	20.940	20.940	0	0	1.000	1.089	20	20	0.174	
Anchors for special mark	Steel	kg	300.000	300.000	300.000	300.000	0	0	1.000	1.089	10	10	0.174	
	Chain	kg	665.000	665.000	332.500	332.500	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	10	10	0.380	
	Shackles	kg	2.600	2.600	1.300	1.300	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	5	5	0.380	
	Ballasts	kg	600.000	600.000	600.000	600.000	0	0	1.000	1.089	20	20	0.174	
	Trawl Float	kg	165.000	165.000	82.500	82.500	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	10	10	0.380	
Site markings	Grid Riser Rope + Extension Arm	kg	37.026	37.026	37.026	37.026	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174	
	Double Figure 8 Through Trawl Float	kg	10.890	10.890	10.890	10.890	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174	
	Prusik knot (Grid-Riser Connection)	kg	2.244	2.244	2.244	2.244	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174	
Moorings	Oyster Long Line	kg	136.500	136.500	34.125	34.125	0	0.75	0.625	1.089	5	5	0.483	
	AP6 Baskets	kg	1,258.400	1,258.400	0.000	0.000	0.25	0.75	0.500	1.089	5	5	0.587	
Cultivation material	Rope Bridal	kg	17.889	17.889	4.472	4.472	0	0.75	0.625	1.089	2	2	0.483	
	Nylon Spinner	kg	29.040	29.040	0.000	0.000	0	1	0.500	1.089	10	10	0.587	
King scallop	Stacked Lantern Basket Layer	kg	959.200	0.000	0.000	0.000	0	1	0.000	1.089	5	5	1.000	
	Hanging Rope	kg	58.080	58.080	14.520	14.520	0	0.75	0.625	1.089	2	2	0.483	
TOTAL			kg	12,175.876	10,290.504	6,657.088	6,657.088		0.787	1.089			0.349	

Annex Table 3 Scotland IMTA-lab LTA improved scenario MCI results

					Virgin feedstock	Waste					Linearity	Utility			Material Circularity Indicator
INFRASTRUCTURE					Mass of virgin material (V)	Unrecoverable waste (W)	Unrecoverable waste (WO)	Fraction of mass collected for recycling (Cr)	Fraction of mass for reuse (Cu)	Linear Flow Index (LFI)	Utility factor (X)	Lifetime (L)	Lifetime average (Lav)	Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)	
		Material Type	Unit	Total mass											
Seaweed	Moorings	Anchor	Galvanised steel	kg	2,400.000	2,400.000	2,400.000	2,400.000	0	0	1.000	1.089	10	10	0.174
		Anchor chain	Steel	kg	1,938.000	1,938.000	969.000	969.000	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	10	10	0.380
		Anchor line	Polysteel (32mm)	kg	445.091	445.091	445.091	445.091	0	0	1.000	1.089	10	10	0.174
		Node Ring	Galvanised steel. Cast steel	kg	594.000	594.000	297.000	297.000	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	5	5	0.380
		Shackle	Galvanised steel. High tensile steel	kg	43.650	43.650	21.825	21.825	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	5	5	0.380
		Grid Line	Polysteel (32mm)	kg	300.436	300.436	300.436	300.436	0	0	1.000	1.089	8	8	0.174
		Trawl Float	HDPE	kg	180.000	180.000	90.000	90.000	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	10	10	0.380
		Grid Riser Rope + Extension Arm	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	40.392	40.392	40.392	40.392	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174
		Double Figure 8 Through Trawl Float	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	11.880	11.880	11.880	11.880	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174
	Surface Buoyancy (temporary growing structures)	Prusik knot (Grid-Riser Connection)	Nylon braided (6mm)	kg	2.448	2.448	2.448	2.448	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174
		Rope riser to cushion buoy	Polysteel (32mm)	kg	18.545	18.545	18.545	18.545	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174
			Polystyrene filling,	kg	40.000	40.000	40.000	40.000	0	0	1.000	1.089	8	8	0.174
		Cushion Buoy	Polyethylene shell (8mm thick)	kg	240.000	240.000	240.000	240.000	0	0	1.000	1.089	8	8	0.174
		Cushion Buoy Steel work (incl. shackles, pins, etc.)	Shackle: galvanised steel	kg	200.000	200.000	100.000	100.000	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	3	3	0.380
			Pins: galvanised steel	kg	200.000	200.000	100.000	100.000	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	3	3	0.380
		Polyform Pencil Buoys	Plastic (soft vinyl)	kg	108.000	108.000	27.000	27.000	0	0.75	0.625	1.089	5	5	0.483
		Weights	corroded steel	kg	72.000	0.000	36.000	36.000	0	0.5	0.250	1.089	10	10	0.793
		Riser	Nylon (6mm)	kg	11.178	11.178	11.178	11.178	0	0	1.000	1.089	1	1	0.174
Cultivation materials (temporary)	Seaweed growing lines	Coconut fibre	kg	15.792	0.000	0.000	0.000	0	0	0.000	0.436	1	2.5	1.000	
	Harvest Boxes	Plastic base. Recyclable walls	kg	990.000	247.500	0.000	0.000	0.5	0.5	0.125	1.089	5	5	0.897	
	Twine	Polyester	kg	2.031	2.031	2.031	2.031	0	0	1.000	1.089	1	1	0.174	

				Virgin feedstock	Waste				Linearity	Utility		Material Circularity Indicator		
growing structures)														
	Special mark buoys	HDPE	kg	85.600	85.600	85.600	85.600	0	0	1.000	1.089	20	20	0.174
		Polyurethane	kg	40.920	40.920	40.920	40.920	0	0	1.000	1.089	20	20	0.174
Galvanised Steel		kg	20.940	20.940	20.940	20.940	0	0	1.000	1.089	20	20	0.174	
Site markings	Anchors for special mark	Steel	kg	300.000	300.000	300.000	300.000	0	0	1.000	1.089	10	10	0.174
	Chain	Steel	kg	665.000	665.000	332.500	332.500	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	10	10	0.380
	Shackles	Galvanised steel	kg	2.600	2.600	1.300	1.300	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	5	5	0.380
	Ballasts	Steel	kg	600.000	600.000	600.000	600.000	0	0	1.000	1.089	20	20	0.174
	Trawl Float	HDPE	kg	165.000	165.000	82.500	82.500	0	0.5	0.750	1.089	10	10	0.380
	Grid Riser Rope + Extension Arm	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	37.026	37.026	37.026	37.026	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174
	Double Figure 8 Through Trawl Float	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	10.890	10.890	10.890	10.890	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174
Mooring	Prusik knot (Grid-Riser Connection)	Nylon braided (6mm)	kg	2.244	2.244	2.244	2.244	0	0	1.000	1.089	2	2	0.174
	Oyster Long Line	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	136.500	136.500	34.125	34.125	0	0.75	0.625	1.089	5	5	0.483
Cultivation material	AP6 Baskets	Polypropylene	kg	1,258.400	1,258.400	0.000	0.000	0.25	0.75	0.500	1.089	5	5	0.587
	Rope Bridal	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	17.889	17.889	4.472	4.472	0	0.75	0.625	1.089	2	2	0.483
	Nylon Spinner	Nylon	kg	29.040	29.040	0.000	0.000	0	1	0.500	1.089	10	10	0.587
	Stacked Lantern Basket Layer	HDPE	kg	959.200	0.000	0.000	0.000	0	1	0.000	1.089	5	5	1.000
King scallop Cultivation material														
	Hanging Rope	Polysteel (12mm)	kg	58.080	58.080	14.520	14.520	0	0.75	0.625	1.089	2	2	0.483
TOTAL			kg	12,042.772	10,253.280	6,619.864	6,619.864			0.780	1.071			0.355